

LANDSCAPING OF PUBLIC AREAS.**Tashmuxamedova Gulnoza Farxadovna**

Architect (researcher-educator)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7110090>**Abstract**

The well-being of the urban environment, the formation of artistic, aesthetic and psychological influence on a person depends on the professionalism of architects and the ability of operational organizations to maintain a well-maintained and well-groomed appearance of urban space. The specifics of the structure and formation of urban space naturally flow into one another, forming a single spatial structure of the city.

Keywords: Green areas of the city, pedestrian accessibility, improvement of air quality, scale, air temperature.

Green areas of the city, including landscaped green areas of general use, and natural green areas of special purpose, as well as green areas of limited use, with territorial and unity of the planning organization functional interconnection.

Pedestrian accessibility from residential buildings to green areas on an area of 14-55 hectares, should be designed for daily use, 5-10 minutes walking distance from residential buildings. This green area does not represent the regulation of green areas of narrow use and special purpose, for example, the territories of institutions of higher education, gardening, places of worship, healthcare, the private sector, etc. An exception is made for school territories if residents have access to them outside of school hours. The placement of green areas of general use is focused on solving the following tasks: - comfortable criteria for outdoor recreation and leisure. - accessibility of green areas;

For recreation purposes, it is necessary to take into account: the location of playgrounds for relaxing holidays, games and sports, the arrangement of walking routes. In order to improve the air quality and microclimate near residential buildings, it is necessary to take into account the intensity of landscaping due to the density of planting trees (over 100 pcs. / ha) and shrubs (over 1000 pcs. / ha), the use of tree species with a large volume and density of the crown (oak, maple, ash. Maintaining the scale in limiting the area of squares (up to 1 ha) involves placing, along with landscaping, recreational elements that cannot be equipped in the courtyards of adjacent neighborhoods. It should provide; - acoustic convenience for citizens (due to the remoteness of playgrounds and recreation from the windows of residential buildings), playgrounds for children under seven years old; - the availability of recreational

infrastructure within walking distance; skateparks, table tennis courts, etc. Placement of boulevards in residential and multifunctional areas.

To form boulevards and linear landscaping along the streets unite green spaces; parks and squares. Thus, it increases the availability of green areas from each residential building, and the maintenance of the existing diversity of the ecosystem. To increase the quality of acoustic and microclimatic comfort, an important role is played by the improvement of outdoor recreation and leisure.

For the production of oxygen and the absorption of carbon dioxide, the planting of vegetation plays a huge role. Planting shrubby and high-stemmed vegetation that absorbs noise and retains dust particles. The larger the volume of the crown of trees and shrubs, the more they absorb carbon dioxide and produce oxygen. The standard suggests forming linear landscaping by adjusting the step of tree planting. The effect of noise-proof relief, as a blockage of noise and dust from the roadway. Such a solution is used, for example, in places where school and kindergarten sites adjoin local streets.

On hot days, precipitation naturally absorbs into the ground, thereby moisture evaporates for a long time from the surface of lawns and ground coverings, reducing the air temperature. Reduce the cost of cleaning in winter, reduce the removal and disposal in green areas for snow storage allows. Such zones are usually located in relief depressions. During the melting of snow, ponds are formed in them. Further, the moisture partially evaporates and is absorbed into the soil, providing irrigation for plants. Reducing the load on storm sewers, serves as an effective collection and storage of surface runoff water. On the territory of residential and multifunctional buildings, natural absorption of rainwater runoff is useful for landscaped areas. Provision of acoustic and microclimatic comfort and regulation of rain runoff.

Literature:

1. Bell 1968 Bell V. The city, the suburb and the theory of social choice // New urbanization / edited by S. Greer. New York: Putnam Books, 1968. pp. 132-168.
2. Bourdieu 1984 Bourdieu P. Distinction. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1984.
3. Butler and Robson, 2003. Butler T., Robson B. A Call to London, the Middle Classes and the Remaking of Inner London. Oxford:
4. Berg, 2003. Buzar, Ogden and Hall, 2005
5. Buzar S., Ogden P.E., Hall R. Everyday issues: The Quiet Demography of urban transformation. Progress // Human Geography. 2005. No. 29. pp. 413-436.
6. Clark 2003 Clark D.B. Consumer society and the postmodern city. London: Routledge, 2003.

7. Fishman 1994 Fishman R. Urban and suburban areas: Rethinking "Berbs" // American Quarterly. 1994. No. 46. pp. 35-39.
8. Florida 2002 Florida R. The emergence of the creative class and how it transforms work, leisure, society and everyday life. New York: Basic Books, 2002.
9. Hans 1967 Hans H. Levittownians. London: Allen Lane, 1967.
10. Hans 1968 Hans H. J. Urbanism and suburbanism as ways of life: a reassessment of definitions // Readings in the sociology of the city / edited by R.E. Pal. Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1968. pp. 95-118.
11. Hegerstrand 1982. Hegerstrand T. Diorama, path and project. Tijdschrift // Economische en Sociale Geografie. 1982. No. 73. pp. 323-339.
12. Hayer and Reindorp, 2001. Hayer M., Reindorp A. In search of a new public domain. Rotterdam: Nai Uitgevers, 2001.
13. Helbrecht 2004 Helbrecht I. Naked geographies in the knowledge of society — creative cities as a text and a work of art: Two eyes, one vision // Artificial environment. 2004. No. 30. pp. 194-203.
14. Jarvis, Pratt and Wu, 2001. Jarvis H., Pratt A., Wu P. The secret life of cities, social reproduction of everyday life. Harlow: Pearson Education Ltd., 2001.
- Karsten 2007 Karsten L. Housing as a way of life: on the way to understanding the preferences of middle-class families for urban residential development // Housing Research. 2007. No. 22. pp. 83-98.
15. Latham 1999. Latham A. Powers of participation: about being engaged, being not indifferent, and to urban life // District. 1999. No. 31. pp. 161-168.
16. Maffesoli 1996 Maffesoli M. Time of the Tribes: The Decline of Individualism in mass society. London: Sage, 1996.

Sites:

1. Book 1. A set of principles for the integrated development of urban areas
<http://ivo.garant.ru/#/document/72241292>
2. <https://minstroy.midural.ru/uploads/01%20%D0%9A%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B3%D0%B0%201%20%D1%81%D0%B2%D0%BE%D0%B4%20%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BD%D1%86%D0%B8%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%B2%20%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BC%D0%BF%D0%BB%D0%B5%D0%BA%D1%81%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%B3%D0%BE%20%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B2%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B8%D1%8F%20%D0%B3%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B4%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B8%D1%85%20%D1%82%D0%B5%D1%80%D1%80%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%BE%D0%B8%D0%B9.pdf>

3. <https://minstroy.midural.ru/uploads/02%20%D0%9A%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B3%D0%B0%202%20%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B4%D0%B0%D1%80%D1%82%20%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B2%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B8%D1%8F%20%D0%B7%D0%B0%D1%81%D1%82%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%BD%D1%8B%D1%85%20%D1%82%D0%B5%D1%80%D1%80%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%B9.pdf>

4. http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/hlm/prgm/cph/experts/uzbekistan/02_housing_and_construction/%D0%9A%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%BA%D0%B8%D0%B9_%D0%BE%D0%B1%D0%B7%D0%BE%D1%80_24_02_2014.pdf

5. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF REDUCING THE DISCREPANCY BETWEEN THE TERMS OF PHYSICAL AND MORAL DETERIORATION OF HOUSING.

6. <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=38255214>

7. PROBLEMS OF CONSTRUCTION OF LOW-RISE RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS IN THE CITY OF TASHKENT.

8. <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=38255231>